

Impact of Goods and Services Tax on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises – A Study

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Abstract

Goods and Services Tax (GST) is an indirect tax which was introduced in India on 1 July 2017 and was applicable throughout India which replaced multiple cascading taxes levied by the central and state governments. It's true that GST means „Great Step towards Transformation’, ‘Great Step towards Transparency’ in India and it is also true that someone gives ‘birth’ while someone else nurtures it. It has been long pending problem to streamline all the specific types of oblique taxes and put into effect a ‘single taxation’ system. Because the name indicates, the GST could be levied each on items and offerings. GST is a tax that needs to pay on supply of products & offerings. Any person, who is presenting or offering goods and services, is liable to fee GST. Now we are witnessing, how this tax reform reshapes our economy and business dynamics for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Flourishing amidst a challenging environment, the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) of India experienced several highs and lows in the past few years. With the Indian economy expected to emerge as one of the leading economies in the world and likely to become a \$5 trillion economy by 2025, major impetus is being given to strengthen the back bone of our economy-the SME sector. This paper highlights to know the GST and MSMEs and Impact of GST and MSMEs.

Introduction

The initial attempt to implement GST in India was made on November 10, 2009, to give a boost to complicated tax structure and create a stock market. Any deadlines have already been set to implement GST in India, but all have been extended due to several obstacles in its way. GST is recognised as a destination based consumption tax, in which the consumption states are liable for revenues as the origin states are likely to get 1% additional tax for at least two years. It is considered to be a significant improvement over the pre-existing middle excise duty at the political level and the sales tax policy at the state level; the new tax will be a further considerable invention and the next logical step towards comprehensive indirect tax reform in the country. The implementation of GST will improve

the tax income for the Government, and it would close the distortions of differential methods of manufacturing and service sector. Several Taxes, like central sales tax, Octroi, turnover tax, state levels sales tax, etc., will be pounded below one ambit GST. It will also serve to curb inflation as the tax rate under the GST regime will remain constant over some time.

The recommended GST is likely to change the whole scenario of the current indirect tax system. It is considered as the most significant tax reform since 1947. Currently, in India, the complicated indirect tax system is followed with imbrications of taxes imposed by union and states separately. GST will unify all the incidental charges under an umbrella and will form a smooth national market. Experts say that GST will help the economy to grow more efficiently by raising the tax group as it will disrupt all the tax barriers between states and integrate the country via a single tax rate. GST was first suggested by France in 1954, and now it is followed by 160 countries. Most nations followed unified GST, while some nations, such as Brazil and Canada, developed a dual GST scheme where primary taxation is enforced and both states. In India also the second method of GST is proposed, including CGST and SGST& implement from 1st July 2017.

The Rajyasabha consistently moved the Constitution (22nd amendment) bill 2014, on 3rd August 2016 with 203 votes in this bill's support. All parties, except the AIADMK, upheld the law. Production of sales of goods and services during India, to replace taxes levied by central Govt and GST is an indirect tax on the consumption. And State Govt. GST is levied and received at each stage of sale or marketing of services and goods. It has a method of Input Tax Credit which will allow sellers to maintain the paid tax so that the last liability on the edge consumer is reduced. It is the most significant tax reform in 70 years after the independence of India, the Services Tax (GST) and goods were finally started on the midnight of 30 June 2017, though the process of forming the law took 17 years (since 2000 when it was first introduced). It's been launched at midnight 30 June – 1 July 2017 session in both the houses of parliament assembled at the Hall of the Parliament, but which was immediately boycotted by the opposition by staging a walkout to show their rejection of the same.

Before 1st July 2017, any taxes did levy by the state Govt. and some were collected by central Govt. Govt. levied only one combined tax rate instead of all various kinds of taxes, GST is applied on goods and services at the site where real consumption happens. It is based on the Purpose Principle. GST levied and received at each stage of sale or procurement of goods and services. Products and services are not distinguished and are taxed at a single rate in a supply chain until the goods and services reach the consumer. It is the consumer of products and services who bears the tax. The production /wholesaler /retailer pays the applicable GST rate but can claim back through tax credit mechanism.

GST in India

GST will go to win n number of taxes levied on our destruction from entertainment tax to sales tax, excise duty, VAT, luxury tax and import duty. GST will help to defeat the problem of double assessment as under this tax will be levied on the number of goods and services as it is based on "Destination Principle" which suggests tax will be levied at the spot of final destruction. GST will be collected at the last Period of Sale.

The Government of India is in the method of using a Dual System GST comprising of two ingredients: Central Goods and Service Tax (CGST)

State Goods and Service Tax (SGST)

Intra-state supply and consumption of goods & services

Inter-state movement of goods

Import of Goods & Services

The Arrival of GST

The GST is an increase in the comprehensive tax reforms in the country and would give India a world-class tax method and improve tax collections by the integration of goods and services tax. It would end distortions of differential methods of service sector and manufacturing. It will lead to the cancellation of taxes such as central sales tax, octroi, state-level entry tax, stamp duty, sales tax, telecom license fees, turnover tax, tax on consumption or sale of electricity, etc. GST is expected to create a business-friendly environment, as price levels, and hence, inflation rates would come down over time as an average tax rate is applied. It will also improve the government's fiscal health as the tax collection system would become more transparent, making tax evasion difficult. The GST at the central and at the state level will, hence, agriculture, give more help to the industry, trade and consumers through a more extensive and inclusion of some charges in the GST and more far-reaching coverage of input tax set off and service fee set off, and phasing out of CST a way will help eliminate the defects of VAT.

Experts have Enlisted the Benefits of GST as under

- It would introduce the two-tiered One-Country-One-Tax management.
- It would subsume all indirect rates at the centre and the state level.
- It would not only widen the tax administration by covering services and tax services but also make it transparent.
- It would free the manufacturing sector from the cascading effect of taxes, thus by increase the cost-competitiveness of goods and services.
- It would bring down the prices of services and goods and thus by, improve consumption.
- It would create a business-friendly atmosphere, thus by increase tax-GDP ratio.
- It would become the ease of doing business in India.

There appear to be certain loopholes in the proposed GST tax regime which may be detrimental in delivering the desired results. They are:

India has adopted dual GST preferably of national GST. It has made the whole structure of GST somewhat complicated in India. The centre will have to coordinate with 29 states and seven union territories to implement such a tax regime. Such a system is likely to create economic as well as political issues. The rules are likely to lose the say in determining rates once GST is implemented. The sharing of revenues between the countries and the centre is still a matter of contention with no consensus arrived regarding neutral revenue rate.

Chief Economic Advisor Arvind Subramanian on 4 December 2015 suggested GST rates of 12% for concessional goods, 17-18% for standard products and 40% for luxury goods which is much higher than the present maximum service tax rate of 14%. Such an initiative is likely to push inflation.

The proposed GST structure is likely to succeed only if the country has a strong IT network. It is a well-known reality that India is still budding as far as internet connectivity is concerned. Moreover, the proposed regime seems to ignore the emerging sector of e-commerce. E-commerce does not give signs of the business outside the internet and has anonymity associated with it. As a result, it becomes almost painful to track the business transaction taking place through the internet, which can be business to business, activity to customer or customer to customer. Again, there seems to be no evidence as to whether a product should be considered a service or a product under the concept of E-commerce. New techniques can be developed to track such transactions, but until such technologies become readily accessible, the generation of tax revenue from this sector would continue to be uncertain and much below the expectation. Again E-commerce has been insulated against taxation under custom duty moratorium on electronic transmissions by the WTO

Bali Ministerial Conference held in 2014 [4]. Communication is considered to be a necessity, and one cannot do without discussion. In modern times, communication has assumed the dimension of telecommunication.

GST and MSMEs

The increasing formalisation of the Indian economy, primarily through digitisation, cash transactions of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) and is an inexorable advance that will upend the business model based on the twin arbitrage of labour. India's paradigm shift to the Services Tax (GST) and Goods regime in July will increase their compliance charges and snare a preponderance of them into the indirect For the first time, tax net.

Sharp Practices

So far, unorganised MSMEs have grown quicker than planned peers because of lower cost structures stemming from tax delay, and not having to pay social security benefits to employees (such as provident gratuity and fund), and excise duty (if turnover is less than Rs.1.5 crore). Some MSMEs also understate the employee base or set up multiple experiments to avoid breaching tax thresholds. Such sharp studies helped them price products and services competitively over the past few decades and also maintained operating margins at organised player levels.

The alterations resulting from the impact of GST are many. To wit, for companies, the reduction in the entrance for GST exemption to 20 lakh from 1.5 crores involves tens of thousands of disorganised MSMEs will soon be cast into the tax net. And digital transaction trails designed by dual authentication of inventories under GST will strengthen tax agreement. Additionally, a moderate tax burden under GST will decrease the cost of logistics and raw materials.

Different for Services

For the services area, though, the tax burden will grow. Hence, established members with the ability to hold their price-lines, or pass on any increase in cost to customers, will be able to maintain or improve profit margins. We believe a simplified tax structure and a unified market will improve operational efficiencies, especially of MSMEs with a broader range. Then repeat, there was demonetisation. Last fiscal, MSMEs were expected to record on-year top-line increase of 14 to 16 per cent.

However, the impact of demonetisation has been severe in the second half, and they would have closed the year with an increase of just 6 to 8 per cent. But as the effects of demonetisation fade, growth will pick up in the current fiscal.

A peep into outlook: Positive for light engineering: Light engineering MSMEs rated by Crisil saw 15 per cent compound annual growth rate in topline between fiscals 2014 and 2016, with demonetisation causing just a blip. GST is expected to provide a boost to this segment because of lower tax incidence. The Government's thrust on 'Make in India' will also lead to continued investments, helping the sector maintain growth momentum.

Positive for electrical equipment: Sales in companies rated by Crisil grew way faster at about 23 per cent in fiscal 2016 compared with 16 per cent in 2015. The sector will benefit from lower freight costs and tax rates. Though growth is assumed to be active this fiscal, especially from China, cheaper imports, remain a challenge.

Neutral for pharmaceuticals: Sales in companies ranked by Crisil grew 11 per cent in fiscal 2016 compared with 15 per cent in 2015. Demonetisation had a limited impact as the Government had allowed extended use of the banned Rs.500 and Rs.1, 000 currency notes for purchasing medicines. We do not foresee any significant difference in tax rates under GST. This fiscal, too, we expect similar growth.

Neutral for auto components: Within fiscals 2014 and 2016, sales by unorganised auto component makers rated by Crisil grew at 14 per cent annually compared with 7 per cent for their organised peers. However, demonetisation led to a short-term drop in sales to original equipment manufacturers (OEMs), or vehicle makers. This fiscal, OEM sales are expected to normalise. Organised players will benefit and record moderate growth given the thrust on digitisation and lower tax rates under GST. Unorganised players catering mostly to the non-OEM replacement market will be forced to move into the organised domain.

Marginally negative for textiles: Sales growth in the textiles-related MSME segment had already declined from 15 per cent in fiscal 2015 to 8 per cent in 2016. GST will have a marginally negative impact because of the higher tax rates required. During Crisis's interactions with clients, some of them raised concerns that a unified market would create more competition in an already crowded and price-sensitive arena with a large number of unorganised players. Organised players dealing in branded apparel are expected to fare well, though. The sector is expected to record the below-par growth of 5 per cent or below.

Marginally negative for leather and footwear sectors: Companies Crisil rates in this segment have seen muted growth and have borne the brunt of demonetisation. With competition, including from Chinese players being active, the operating margin has fallen to as low as 6 per cent for organised players. We do not expect GST rates to vary much from the current indirect tax rates. Crisil expects overall growth and margins of players to remain subdued this fiscal.

Monthly and Financial Representation of Development Commission, MSME

Under various Promotional and development activities taken up as part of plan schemes, the number of MSMEs reported to be benefitted during November 2017 was 4,985 as compared to 3,139 during the same period of last year. 20,114 persons were trained in November 2017 as compared to 9,351 persons in November 2016. The numbers of claims of credit proposals approved are 15,920 during Nov. '17 as against 25,971 during the month of November 2016.

Impact of GST on MSME

At present, the total tax collection in India is about 14.5 Lakh Crore, of which 34% is an indirect tax. Indirect taxes include service tax, stump duty, customs duty, VAT, etc. It refers to the collection of tax indirectly by the Government of India. In most of the developing countries, the share of indirect tax is higher than the direct tax. However, in developed countries, the percentage of indirect tax is much lower. Therefore, the new GST implementation will allow the government to have a better grip on the taxpayers. This should be capable of developing the entire tax system.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have been recognised as the primary growth driver of Indian economics for decades. It is further apparent from the fact that today we have around 3 million SMEs in India, providing almost 50% of the industrial output and 42% of India's total export. For a developing country like India and its demographic diversity, SMEs have emerged as the leading employment-generating sector and has contributed balanced development across industries. Let's explore what would be the impact of GST on Medium & Small Enterprises.

All the compliance procedures under GST — Certification, Refunds, Payments and Returns will now be carried out through online gateways only, and thus SMEs must not worry about interacting with department managers for taking out these compliances, which are considered as a headache in the current tax regime.

The Direct Impact of GST on Small and Medium Businesses

GST will help and guide the method of beginning a business in India. Earlier, every company in India was required to obtain VAT registration, which differs in every state, and the rules and regulations are different. Thus it was a very complicated system. However, under GST, the companies have to only register for GST, which will have a centralized process, similar to service tax.

Currently, for any business, it is necessary to make a VAT payment if the annual turnover is more than 5 lakh in a few states and ten lakhs in few other countries. This variation in various states creates trouble. Under GST, a business hasn't got to register or collect GST if the yearly turnover is 10 lakh. This applies to every country. This will allow many small companies which have a turnover between 5 lakh – 10 lakh to avoid using for the GST return.

GST allows medium and small business to do business with the facility in India, due to the less complexity. The contrast between the services and goods will be gone, and this will make compliance easier.

Impact of GST on e-commerce

The e-commerce sector in India has frequently been contributing to the Indian economy, and to reap the advantages of a mature and a rewarding e-commerce sector, a stable indirect tax arrangement is required as a panacea to several tax maladies encountered by the e-commerce companies in retail space.

GST implementation is also required to resolve many supply chain issues faced by the e-commerce companies enabling faster shipment and returns and decreased paperwork. This is also going to happen help the companies to Make things better supply chain plans with an improved focus on improving warehousing, and network settlements would be service driven and purely cost. The dual structure of GST will also bring in transparency and simplification of the tax method makes it peaceful and prompt for those selling across states, thus lowering the burden of consumers.

The following Chart shows SEZ Approvals after Introducing GST in India

Benefits of GST Implementation

- It will make the taxation method more transparent, easy to understand and straightforward.
- It will reduce the overall cost of services and goods to the final consumer as cascading effect of taxation will be overcome.
- It will facilitate the free flow of services and goods and thereby decreasing overall transaction cost.
- Since GST is not levied on services and goods which are transported, so it provides an incentive to EOUs, SEZs and EPZs. And GST will be collected on products or services imported into the country with the objective principle where the imported services or goods are applied that state will enjoy the tax revenue since mediators in the supply chain can claim the tax credit which will reduce the charge of preparing a business.
- It will decrease the scope of corruption in the economy as a whole.
- GST will ensure the consistency of taxes over the states, irrespective of place of production or consumption.
- The normal taxation rate on organisations will fall, which will reduce the expenses of Indian goods and services and ultimately, GDP would grow and make them competitive in the global market.
- It will improve the tax base as more firms will come under the tax administration, which ultimately improves the tax revenue collection for the government.
- The taxation burden will be manufacturing and services, through a lower tax rate between divided equitably by expanding the tax base and minimizing exemptions.
- For paying GST, 13/15 digit PAN-linked license in line with Income tax will be allotted which will ease the tax payment system

Requests for Implementing the Services & Goods Tax System

- Determining start limit is a great request right now as low limit will bother service providers and small scale traders, but high revenue for government whereas high threshold limit will result in less revenue for the government due to narrow tax base.
- A lot of changes at planning and implementation level will be required where administration to be made in line with IT infrastructure.
- To implement GST, cooperation from the state government is required as the states where production of services and goods are high will enjoy more income than countries which have low use of products and services.
- Determination of the rate of tax on goods and services is an excellent challenge for the government due to the problem of consensus between centre and state in this regard.
- Massive expenditure on IT support including Tax Information Exchange System (TINXSYS), enabling voluntary compliance and is expected that too in a time bound manner for enhancing operational efficiency improving tax payer's convenience
- Since there will be the binary form of GST, so there will be another tax charges at Centre level, State level and there a further community of these taxes will be complicated depending upon demand, location and resources of each state.

Conclusion

Although the GST implementation aims to upsurge the taxpayer base, largely SMEs into its opportunity, it presents a problem of compliance and related charges for them. Several policy interventions along with technology and innovation will continue to play vital role in creating a business-friendly atmosphere for the SMEs. No doubt that GST is aimed to increase the taxpayer

base, majorly SMEs into its scope and will put a burden of compliance and associated costs to them. But in the long run, GST will turn these SMEs more competitive with a level playing field between large enterprises and them. In fact, recently government has also formed a special committee to look after the issues faced by MSME sector in GST. It is urged to the industry that they proactively highlight the above issues and obtain the relief prior to advent of GST as once GST is implemented; the chances of respite would be very minimal for the sector. Furthermore, these Indian SMEs would be able to compete with foreign competition coming from cheap cost centers such as China, Philippines and Bangladesh.

Nevertheless, GST will make the MSMEs more competitive in the long run and will make the playing arena level between big enterprises and them. Additionally, the Indian MSMEs would be able to compete with the international market goods and competition coming from cheap price epicenters such as China, Philippines and Bangladesh and actually thrive in the world market scenario.

References

1. R. Lavanya Kumari. (2017). Impact of goods and service tax (GST) on Indian MSMEs. *International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences*, 7(7), 334-348
2. Rani Jacob. (2017). The impact of goods and service tax on the micro, small and medium enterprises. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 3(10), 86-66.
3. Dr. I.Siddiq & Dr. K.Sathya Prasad. (2017). Impact of GST on micro, small and medium enterprises. *Journal of Management and Science*, Special Issue-1, 180-183.
4. Heimonen, T., (2012). What are the factors that affect innovation in growing SMEs? *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 15(1), 122-144.
5. Anubha Vashisht, Amita Chaudhary, & Priyanka. (2016). Role of SMEs in Indian Economy. *International Journal of Management*, 3(Sp. Iss.-1), 14-18.
6. Kumar Nitin, "GOODS AND SERVICES TAX IN INDIA: A WAY FORWARD", *Global Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, Volume 3, Issue 6, May 2014.
7. Sharma Manpreet & Neha, " A STUDY ON GOODS AND SERVICES TAX IN INDIA", *The International Journal's Research Journal of Social Science and Management*, Volume: 03, Number: 10, February-2014,
8. <http://www.cbec.gov.in/htdocs-cbec/gst>
9. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goods_and_Services_Tax_\(India\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Goods_and_Services_Tax_(India))
10. <https://cleartax.in/gst>
11. <http://www.ey.com/in/en/services/ey-goods-and-services-tax-gst>
12. <http://www.gstindia.com/about/>
13. <http://www.siamindia.com/publications.aspx?mpgid=42&pgidtrail=44>
14. <http://www.profitbooks.net/goods-and-service-tax-gst/>